

Chemical Transformations of 6 α -Acetoxyazadirone and Two-dimensional NMR Studies on Tetranortriterpenoids[†]

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Basic hydrolysis of the tetranortriterpenoid 6 α -acetoxyazadirone yielded 6 α -hydroxydeacetylazadirone which on preferential acetylation in the cold afforded 6 α -acetoxydeacetylazadirone. Treatment of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone with hydrogen peroxide-selenium dioxide gave 6-*O*-acetylisonimocinolide which was a constituent of *Chisocheton paniculatus* and it underwent acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine to 6,21-di-*O*-acetylisonimocinolide. Careful hydrogenation of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone gave 1,2-dihydro as well as 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro derivatives which were hydrolysed under basic conditions to the corresponding 6,7-diol. 6 α -Hydroxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirone so derived furnished meldenin, a minor phytoconstituent of *Melia azadirachta*, on preferential acetylation in the cold and a triol upon NaBH₄ reduction. Acetylation of the latter afforded a triacetate. The structures and nmr assignments of the compounds were settled from two-dimensional homonuclear and heteronuclear correlation (optimized for one-bond and long-range C-H couplings) studies.

6 α -Acetoxyazadirone (1), a major constituent of *Chisocheton paniculatus*¹, is an interesting tetranortriterpenoid possessing an α,β -unsaturated ketone moiety, a trisubstituted double bond, a β -substituted furan unit along with two acetoxy groups at C-6 and C-7 positions. As a result it was found to be susceptible to reagents like selenium dioxide¹, alkaline hydrogen peroxide², *N*-bromosuccinimide², sodium borohydride², *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid² and osmium tetroxide². The present investigators intended to utilise 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (1) further and the results of their studies aimed at chemical correlation of 1 with the insect growth regulator meliacins nimocinolide (2) and isonimocinolide (3) isolated previously as minor constituents of *Azadirachta indica*³ and also with the minor tetranortriterpenoid meldenin (4) found in *Melia azadirachta*⁴ and 6-*O*-acetylisonimocinolide⁵ (5) isolated from the seeds of *Chisocheton paniculatus*, are presented here-with.

It has been documented⁵ that treatment of 3-isopropylfuran (6) with *N*-bromosuccinimide generated 4-hydroxy-2-isopropylbut-2-enolide (7) but 4-hydroxy-3-isopropylbut-2-enolide (8) was produced when a peracid was employed as the oxidant. 6 α -Hydroxyazadirone (9) is quite likely to be the intermediate for the meliacins 2 and 3 as similar oxidative modification around the furan unit in 9 would generate them, while 9 could, in turn, be derived from 10 by preferential monoacetylation. Basic hydrolysis of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (1) smoothly afforded a compound, C₂₆H₃₄O₄ (M⁺ 410), m.p. 205°, devoid of acetate moieties (ir, pmr and cmr) but had hydroxyl group (ir) and a newly generated -CH-CHOH-CHOH- unit (pmr, COSY) and in conformity with the formation of 6 α -hydroxydeace-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.
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tylazadirone (**10**). Treatment of the diol **10** with acetic anhydride-pyridine at about ice-cold temperature for 20 h afforded mainly a monoacetylated product (ir, pmr, COSY) along with some of the diacetylated derivative identical with 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (**1**). A careful analysis of the pmr spectrum of the monoacetylated product **11** revealed that the proton resonance at δ 4.16 (1H, br d, J 11.6 Hz, H-6) in **10** has suffered significant downfield shift (~1.30 ppm) in consonance with a preferential acetylation of the equatorial hydroxyl group at C-6. Compound **9**, the required intermediate for the generation of the plant insect growth regulator meliacins nimocinolide (**2**) and isonimocinolide (**3**) through oxidative modification of its furan system, that was likely to be formed upon selective acetylation of the C-7 hydroxyl could not be isolated even in traces.

It has been observed that treatment of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (**1**) with hydrogen peroxide-selenium dioxide in *t*-BuOH and stirring for about 3 h gave a product which was devoid of β -substituted furan unit present in **1**. Instead it showed pmr signals (d_5 -pyridine) at δ 6.00 (1H, s, H-22) and 6.40 (1H, s, H-21) and cmr signals at δ 100.3 (d, C-21), 119.6 (d, C-22), 170.5 (s, C-20) and 173.2 (s, C-23) commensurate with the presence of a 3-substituted-4-hydroxy-but-2-enolide moiety. Since all other pmr and cmr signals as in **1** were present, the product was identified as 6-*O*-acetylisonimocinolide (**5**). It underwent acetylation to 6,21-di-*O*-acetylisonimocinolide (**12**). Compound **5** was reported previously⁵ from the seeds of *Chisocheton paniculatus* and was characterised as its acetate. Further experiments to correlate **1** with **2** and **3** are in progress.

Careful hydrogenation of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (**1**) afforded two components which were separated by column chromatography. The less polar fraction identified as compound **13**, C₃₀H₄₀O₆ (M⁺ 496), m.p. 236°, was devoid of conjugated double bond (ir, pmr, cmr). The polar component, C₃₀H₄₄O₆, m.p. 210°, had no conjugated double bond, as also the β -substituted furan unit. Instead, a tetrahydrofuran unit was there and the cmr spectrum of the polar component adduced for the presence of a pair of compounds (**14a, b**) epimeric at C-17 in it. 6 α -Acetoxy-1,2-dihydroazadirone (**13**) was hydrolysed under basic condition to 6 α -hydroxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirone (**15**), C₂₆H₃₆O₄, m.p. 205°. Similar hydrolysis of **14 (a, b)** yielded **16 (a, b)**. Controlled acetylation of **15** afforded, along with some 6 α -acetoxy-1,2-dihydroazadirone (**13**), a product, C₂₈H₃₈O₅ (M⁺ 454), m.p. 240°, which was characterised as 6 α -acetoxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirone (**4**) (ir, pmr, cmr and mass) having the structure assigned to the minor tetranortriterpenoid meldenin⁴ found in *Melia azadirachta*. Careful catalytic reduction of **11** produced a 1,2-dihydro derivative which was identical with meldenin⁴ **4**. Sodium

borohydride reduction of 6 α -hydroxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirone (**15**) afforded the product **17**², C₂₆H₃₈O₄ (M⁺ 414), m.p. 191°, which underwent acetylation to the triacetate **18**, C₃₂H₄₄O₇, m.p. 163°, upon treatment with Ac₂O-pyridine.

The proton and carbon chemical shift assignments reported in this paper were arrived at from a combination of homonuclear as well as heteronuclear correlation studies on compounds **4**, **5**, **10-16** prepared as also on 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (**1**) for use as model. Information about the proton network in all the compounds was secured from two-dimensional ¹H-¹H correlation studies⁷⁻⁹. It particularly allowed identification of the coupling network of ¹H signals associated with (i) H-1 and H-2 in the enones, (ii) H-5, H-6 and H-7, (iii) H-15, H_a-16, H_b-16 and H-17, (iv) H-9, H₂-11 and H₂-12 and (v) H-21, H-22 and H-23 (in compounds having β -substituted furan moiety). Two-dimensional ¹³C-¹H correlation experiments¹⁰ optimized for one-bond ¹³C-¹H coupling then identified the signal of a protonated carbon with the signal/s of the proton/s directly linked with. Thus it was observed that the proton resonances at δ 7.16 (d, H-1), 7.37 (br s, H-23), 7.23 (br s, H-21), 5.92 (d, H-2), 5.38 (m, H-15) and 6.27 (br s, H-22) in **1** displayed one-bond heteronuclear correlation with the *sp*² hybridized methine carbon signals at δ 156.8, 142.3, 139.4, 125.8, 119.4 and 110.7 respectively, in support of their association with C-1, C-23, C-21, C-2, C-15 and C-22. The *sp*³ hybridized methine carbon resonances at δ 47.7, 37.1 and 51.4 correlated with proton resonances at δ 2.55 (d, H-5), 2.27 (m, H-9) and 2.81 (br d, H-17) respectively, while those at δ 69.6 and 74.3 showed correlation with pmr signals at δ 5.45 (br d, H-6) and 5.47 (br s, H-7) in support of their association with C-5, C-9, C-17, C-6 and C-7 respectively. Similarly, methylene carbons C-11, C-12 and C-15 were associated with resonances at δ 16.2, 32.5 and 34.1 respectively, as they displayed correlation spots with signals for H₂-11 (δ 1.70 m, 1.90 m), H₂-12 (1.64 m, 1.70 m) and H₂-16 (2.37 m, 2.47 m). Thus the aforesaid observations conclusively identified the C-2 resonance from C-15, C-6 from C-7, C-16 from C-11 and C-12. The methyl carbon resonances at δ 20.1, 20.4, 20.5, 26.5 and 31.3 were linked to proton resonances for H₃-28, H₃-18, H₃-19, H₃-30 and H₃-29 at δ 1.19, 0.88, 1.19, 1.33 and 1.26 respectively. Further, a long-range two-dimensional heteronuclear correlation experiment¹⁰ optimized for small C-H couplings (around 4-7 Hz) identified signals for protons which were two or three bonds away from the signal of the carbon in question. The methyl proton signal at δ 1.19 (3H, s) in **1** showing three-bond correlation with C-1 resonance at δ 156.8 (d) was thus for H₃-19. The quaternary carbon reso-

TABLE 1—CARBON-13 NMR SIGNALS OF SOME TETRANORTRITERPENOIDS*

Carbon	1	4	5**	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
C-1	156.8	38.1	157.8	157.2	157.0	156.2	38.1	37.7	38.0	38.0	37.6	37.1
C-2	125.8	32.6	125.4	125.9	125.9	126.2	32.7	32.1	32.7	32.2	26.6	22.9
C-3	204.1	217.7	204.3	205.8	204.7	204.1	217.0	216.5	218.9	218.8	78.3	79.9
C-4	44.6	46.3	45.3	45.4	44.7	44.8	46.1	45.7	46.7	46.6	39.0	39.2
C-5	47.7	47.7	48.5	49.3	46.2	47.8	49.1	48.7	51.4	51.3	51.3	50.7
C-6	69.6	72.2	70.4	68.2	71.4	69.6	70.4	70.0	68.3	68.2	69.6	70.2
C-7	74.3	73.3	74.8	75.9	73.4	74.2	74.6	74.1	76.1	76.1	77.1	75.7
C-8	42.8	44.5	43.5	44.8	44.8	43.0	42.6	42.1	43.9	43.8	44.4	42.9
C-9	37.1	39.7	37.7	35.5	35.5	36.9	41.3	40.7	39.6	39.3	41.3	42.9
								40.6		39.2		
C-10	40.5	38.1	41.0	40.6	40.9	40.6	37.9	37.5	37.7	37.7	38.7	37.2
C-11	16.2	16.0	16.6	16.1	16.1	16.2	16.2	15.8	15.9	15.9	16.3	16.3
C-12	32.5	32.3	33.3	32.2	32.2	32.8	32.7	31.8	32.2	32.1	32.1	32.5
								31.1		31.3		
C-13	46.8	47.1	47.8	47.0	47.0	47.3	47.0	46.5	47.0	46.8	47.2	47.1
								46.1		46.4		
C-14	158.0	160.1	158.8	160.7	160.0	157.5	158.1	157.9	160.8	160.7	161.4	158.6
C-15	119.4	120.4	119.6	119.8	120.4	119.2	119.5	119.1	119.7	119.7	119.3	118.9
C-16	34.1	34.3	33.5	34.2	34.2	33.2	34.2	33.1	34.2	33.1	34.1	34.2
								32.8		32.7		
C-17	51.4	51.5	53.4	51.5	51.5	52.7	51.5	58.1	51.4	58.3	51.5	51.3
								57.7		58.0		
C-18	20.4	20.4	21.4	20.2	20.5	20.3	20.4	19.0	20.5	19.3	19.7	19.7
C-19	20.5	16.3	20.7	20.4	20.5	20.5	16.2	15.8	16.1	16.0	16.1	16.4
C-20	124.1	124.2	170.5	124.0	124.0	166.5	124.4	40.4	124.1	40.6	124.2	124.5
								40.1		40.3		
C-21	139.4	139.6	100.3	139.5	139.6	93.1	139.5	72.3	139.5	72.6	139.5	139.5
								71.4		71.7		
C-22	110.7	110.9	119.6	110.8	110.8	120.1	110.9	34.9	110.8	35.1	110.8	110.9
								34.6		34.8		
C-23	142.3	142.5	173.2	142.5	142.5	170.0	142.4	67.9	142.4	68.3	142.4	142.3
								67.7		67.0		
C-28	31.3	31.1	32.0	31.9	31.0	31.5	31.0	30.6	31.7	31.6	30.2	29.8
C-29	20.1	19.4	20.8	20.2	20.4	20.5	19.4	19.3	19.3	19.2	15.1	16.4
C-30	26.5	25.4	26.8	26.7	26.4	26.7	25.6	25.3	25.6	25.6	27.3	27.1
OCOCH ₃	169.8	170.2	170.4		170.2	170.0	170.0	169.5				170.7
	169.8		170.4			169.5	169.9	169.5				170.1
						168.8						169.9
OCOCH ₃	21.0	21.6	21.4	21.6	21.6	21.2	21.1	20.7				21.3
	20.6		20.9			21.2	20.8	20.7				21.0
						20.8						20.8

* $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$ ppm. **In *d*₅-pyridine; $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{d_5\text{-pyridine}(C-2)} + 149.9$ ppm.

nance at δ 40.5 in **1** was linked to C-10 as it showed long-range correlations with proton signals at δ 1.19 (H₃-19), 7.16 (d, H-1), 5.97 (d, H-2) and 2.55 (d, H-5) while that at δ 44.6 was associated with C-4 as it had long-range correlation with proton resonances at δ 1.19 (s, H₃-28), 2.55 (d, H-5) and 5.92 (d, H-2). Again the proton resonances at δ 0.88 (3H, s), 1.33 (3H, s), 1.64–1.70 (2H, m) showed LR X-H correlation with the quarternary carbon resonance at δ

158.0 (C-14) and were thus identified as for those of H₃-18, H₃-30 and H₂-12 respectively. The former proton resonance was for H₃-18 as it showed LR correlation with δ 46.8 (s, C-13) which was further correlating with H-17 (δ 2.81, br d) and H-15 (δ 5.38, m) resonances. A long-range correlation between H-17 resonance (δ 2.81, br d) and C-21 resonance (δ 139.4) in **1** was noted. Using heteronuclear correlations the carbon resonance assignments for **4**, **5**, **10**-

16 (vide Table 1) were made in analogous fashion and those for 17 and 18 followed therefrom.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Column chromatography was carried out with silica gel (60–120 mesh, B.D.H.). Tlc was performed on silica gel G (E. Merck) plates using benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as the solvent system. Samples were crystallized from chloroform-petrol mixture, unless otherwise stated. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. Pmr, cmr, 2D-nmr (XHCORR and LRXHCORR) spectra were run on a Bruker AM 300L supercon spectrometer equipped with ASPECT 3000 computer fitted with an array processor using programme version DISR87.1 or DISR90.1 in CDCl₃ as solvent unless otherwise stated. Multiplicity of carbon signals were established by DEPT experiments. Rotations were measured in a Perkin-Elmer 241 electronic polarimeter in CHCl₃ solutions at 26°. Mass spectra were taken in a Hitachi RMU-6L spectrometer operating at 70 eV.

6 α -Hydroxydeacetylazadirone (10) : 6 α -Acetoxyazadirone (1; 100 mg) was refluxed with 10% methanolic KOH (10 ml) for 50 min on a water-bath. The contents were then cooled and diluted with water (2 ml). After distilling off methanol, water (25 ml) was added and the solution was acidified with dil. HCl. The product was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 \times 25 ml). The combined extracts was washed with saturated brine solution and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of chloroform gave a mass which on crystallisation afforded 6 α -hydroxydeacetylazadirone (10; 76 mg), C₂₆H₃₄O₄, m.p. 205°, [α]_D +46.2°, *R*_f 0.4; ν_{\max} 3530 (OH), 3470 (OH), 1662 (conjugated CO), 872 (furan) cm⁻¹; δ 0.83 (3H, s, H₃-18), 1.11 (3H, s, H₃-19), 1.20 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.37 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.42 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.66 (1H, m, H_a-12), 1.76 (1H, m, H_a-11), 1.95 (2H, m, H_b-11 and H_b-12), 2.22 (1H, m, H-9), 2.30 (1H, d, *J* 11.6 Hz, H-5), 2.45 (2H, m, H_a-16 and OH), 2.58 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 and 10.5 Hz, H_b-16), 2.87 (1H, dd, *J* 10.5 and 7.5 Hz, H-17), 4.00 (1H, br s, H-7), 4.16 (1H, br d, *J* 11.6 Hz, H-6), 5.59 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-15), 5.80 (1H, d, *J* 10.0 Hz, H-2), 6.29 (1H, br s, H-22), 7.10 (1H, d, *J* 10.0 Hz, H-1), 7.27 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.39 (1H, br s, H-23); *m/z* 410 (M⁺, 37%), 395 (8), 392 (9), 377 (14), 359 (8), 325 (27), 315 (93), 214 (13), 213 (41), 145 (64), 135 (75), 136 (13), 121 (69), 85 (100).

Preferential acetylation of 6 α -hydroxydeacetylazadirone (10) to 1,2-dehydromeldenin (11) : 6 α -Hydroxydeacetylazadirone (10; 50 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) was treated with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) at about 0° and the reaction mixture was kept as such for 20 h. It was diluted with ice-cold water (20 ml) and then acidi-

fied with dil. HCl. Extraction with chloroform (3 \times 20 ml), usual work up and removal of chloroform gave a crude mass showing two spots in tlc. Preparative thin layer chromatography of this crude mass on silica gel afforded the monoacetylated compound which on crystallization from chloroform-petrol mixture gave 1,2-dehydromeldenin (11; 20 mg), C₂₈H₃₆O₅, *R*_f 0.5 along with compound 1 (28 mg). Compound 11 showed pmr signals at δ 0.83 (3H, s, H₃-18), 1.17 (3H, s, H₃-19), 1.19 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.28 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.32 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.63 (1H, m, H_a-12), 1.75 (1H, m, H_a-11), 1.94 (2H, m, H_b-11 and H_b-12), 2.18 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.30 (1H, dd, *J* 11.7 and 5.7 Hz, H-9), 2.42 (1H, ddd, *J* 15.5, 7.4 and 2.0 Hz, H_a-16), 2.55 (1H, dd, *J* 15.5 and 10.6 Hz, H_b-16), 2.75 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-5), 2.86 (1H, dd, *J* 10.6 and 7.4 Hz, H-17), 4.08 (1H, br s, H-7), 5.46 (1H, dd, *J* 12.3 and 2.1 Hz, H-6), 5.56 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, H-15), 5.89 (1H, d, *J* 10.1 Hz, H-2), 6.29 (1H, br s, H-22), 7.11 (1H, d, *J* 10.1 Hz, H-1), 7.27 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.39 (1H, br s, H-23).

Oxidation of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (1) to isonimocinolide-6-acetate (5) : 6 α -Acetoxyazadirone (1; 50 mg) in t-BuOH (6 ml) was treated with 20% H₂O₂ (2 ml) and selenium dioxide (4 mg). The mixture was stirred for 3 h using magnetic stirrer. White precipitate formed was collected by filtration. Attempted crystallization afforded isonimocinolide-6-acetate (5) as amorphous material (47 mg), C₃₀H₃₈O₈; ν_{\max} 3260 (OH), 1765 (γ -lactone), 1740 (ester CO), 1650 (conjugated CO), 1225 (C–O–CO) cm⁻¹; pmr δ (*d*₅-pyridine) 0.79 (3H, s, H₃-18), 0.89 (3H, s, H₃-19), 1.05 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.14 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.24 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.64 (2H, m, H₂-11), 1.85 (2H, m, H₂-12), 1.90 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 1.95 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.12 (3H, m, H-9 and H₂-16), 2.46 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-5), 2.90 (1H, m, H-17), 5.10 (1H, m, H-15), 5.40 (1H, br d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-6), 5.50 (1H, br s, H-7), 5.90 (1H, d, *J* 10.1 Hz, H-2), 6.00 (1H, s, H-22), 6.40 (1H, s, H-21) and 7.00 (1H, d, *J* 10.1 Hz, H-1). Compound 5 was also obtained in good yield by simple stirring of 1 (20 mg) in dioxan (2 ml) with 30% H₂O₂ (2 ml) for a prolonged period (more than 36 h).

Acetylation of isonimocinolide-6-acetate (5) : Isonimocinolide-6-acetate (5; 30 mg) was treated with acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) and pyridine (6 drops) and the mixture was kept for 24 h. Cold water was added and the solution was acidified with dil. HCl. Extraction with CHCl₃ (3 \times 25 ml), subsequent work-up and solvent removal gave a crude mass which on purification by tlc afforded diacetylisonimocinolide (12) as glassy material (26 mg), C₃₂H₄₀O₉, [α]_D +109.2°; δ 0.96 (3H, s, H₃-18), 1.16 (6H, s, H₃-19 and H₃-29), 1.27 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.31 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.65 (1H, m, H_a-12), 1.75 (2H, m, H₂-11), 1.85 (1H, m, H_b-12),

2.01 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.03 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.15 (3H, s, 21-OCOCH₃), 2.18 (1H, m, H-9), 2.42 (1H, m, H_a-16), 2.50 (2H, m, H-5 and H_b-16), 2.70 (1H, m, H-17), 5.39 (1H, br s, H-15), 5.42 (1H, br d, *J* 12.1 Hz, H-6), 5.45 (1H, br s, H-7), 5.92 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz, H-2), 6.01 (1H, s, H-22), 6.86 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.10 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz, H-1).

Reduction of 6 α -acetoxyazadirone (1): 6 α -Acetoxyazadirone (100 mg) in ethanol (25 ml) was hydrogenated for 20 min in the presence of Pd-C (10%; 20 mg) at about atmospheric pressure. The catalyst was removed by filtration. Solvent removal from the filtrate gave a crude mass showing two spots in tlc which were separated by column chromatography over silica gel. Benzene eluates afforded a light yellow solid crystallizing in white needles of 6 α -acetoxy-1,2-dihydroazadirone (**13**; 18 mg), C₃₀H₄₀O₆, m.p. 236°, [α]_D +135.6°, *R*_f 0.7. Later benzene eluates gave a light yellow solid which yielded 6 α -acetoxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydroazadirone (**14a,b**) as white crystals (78 mg), C₃₀H₄₄O₆, m.p. 210°, [α]_D +140.5°. Similar hydrogenation experiment with **1** (200 mg) for a shorter period (8 min) improved the yield of **13** (112 mg) over **14a,b** (66 mg). Compound **13** displayed ν_{\max} at 1737 (ester CO), 1710 (CO), 1380, 1365 (*gem* dimethyl), 1255, 1235 (CO-O-C), 875 (furan) cm⁻¹; δ 0.76 (3H, s, H₃-18), 0.86 (3H, s, H₃-19), 1.18 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.25 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.27 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.56 (2H, m, H_a-11 and H_a-12), 1.73 (1H, m, H_b-11), 1.83 (2H, m, H₂-1), 1.85 (1H, m, H_b-12), 1.99 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.00 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.15 (1H, m, H-9), 2.33 (1H, m, H_a-16), 2.35 (1H, m, H_a-2), 2.39 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-5), 2.45 (1H, m, H_b-16), 2.75 (1H, m, H_b-2), 2.80 (1H, m, H-17), 5.26 (1H, dd, *J* 12.2 and 2.7 Hz, H-6), 5.34 (1H, br s, H-15), 5.42 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-7), 6.23 (1H, br s, H-22), 7.20 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.34 (1H, br s, H-23); *m/z* 496 (M⁺, 61%), 481 (2), 436 (6), 393 (3), 376 (87), 361 (74), 348 (5), 213 (18), 146 (15), 145 (53), 81 (100). Compounds **14a,b** showed ν_{\max} at 1740 (ester CO), 1710 (CO), 1380, 1370 (*gem* dimethyl), 1250, 1230 (CO-O-C) cm⁻¹; δ 0.70 (3H, s, H₃-19), 0.85 (3H, s, H₃-29), 0.88 (3H, s, H₃-18), 1.05 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.06 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.25, 1.35 (total 1H, m, H_a-12), 1.37 (1H, m, H_a-22), 1.40 (1H, m, H-17), 1.50 (2H, m, H₂-11), 1.65 (2H, m, H₂-1), 1.50, 1.72 (total 1H, m, H_b-12), 1.82, 1.88 (total 1H, m, H_b-22), 1.85 (1H, m, H_a-16), 1.86 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 1.87 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.00 (1H, m, H_b-16), 2.05 (1H, m, H-9), 2.08 (1H, m, H-20), 2.16 (1H, m, H_a-2), 2.28 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-5), 2.62 (1H, m, H_b-2), 3.06, 3.08 (total 1H, m, H_a-21), 3.58 (1H, m, H_a-23), 3.66 (1H, m, H_b-23), 3.75, 3.81 (total 1H, m, H_b-21), 5.08 (1H, br s, H-15), 5.12 (1H, br d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-6) and 5.23 (1H, br s, H-7).

Hydrolysis of 6 α -acetoxy-1,2-dihydroazadirone (13):

Compound **13** (100 mg) was refluxed with 10% methanolic KOH (10 ml) for 50 min on a water-bath. The contents were then cooled and diluted with water (2 ml). After distilling off methanol, water (25 ml) was added and the solution was acidified with dil. HCl. The product was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 \times 25 ml). Usual work-up and removal of chloroform gave a mass which on crystallization afforded 6 α -hydroxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirone (**15**; 80 mg), C₂₆H₃₆O₄, m.p. 205°, [α]_D +93.3°, *R*_f 0.4; ν_{\max} 3562 (OH), 3555 (OH), 1705 (CO), 1383, 1378 (*gem* dimethyl), 872 (furan) cm⁻¹; δ 0.82 (6H, s, H₃-18 and H₃-19), 1.15 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.34 (6H, s, H₃-28 and H₃-29), 1.49 (1H, m, H_a-12), 1.52 (1H, m, H_a-11), 1.72 (3H, m, H₂-1 and H_b-11), 1.82 (1H, m, H_b-12), 2.06 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0 and 6.0 Hz, H-9), 2.16 (1H, d, *J* 11.3 Hz, H-5), 2.25 (1H, m, H_a-2), 2.36 (1H, m, OH), 2.40 (1H, m, H_a-16), 2.46 (1H, dd, *J* 14.5 and 10.5 Hz, H_b-16), 2.67 (1H, m, H_b-2), 2.80 (1H, dd, *J* 10.5 and 7.4 Hz, H-17), 3.93 (1H, br s, H-7), 4.01 (1H, br d, *J* 11.3 Hz, H-6), 5.54 (1H, br d, *J* 2.4 Hz, H-15), 6.25 (1H, br s, H-22), 7.22 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.35 (1H, br s, H-23).

6 α -Hydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydrodeacetylazadirone (16a,b): Basic hydrolysis of **14a,b** (25 mg) as in the previous case, usual work-up and purification of the reaction product by column chromatography afforded **16a,b**, C₂₆H₄₀O₄, as amorphous material; ν_{\max} 1715 (CO), 1378 (*gem* dimethyl) cm⁻¹; δ 0.82 (3H, s, H₃-19), 0.88 (3H, s, H₃-18), 1.15 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.34 (6H, s, H₃-28 and H₃-29), 3.00-3.85 (4H, m, H₂-21 and H₂-23), 3.94 (1H, br s, H-7), 4.03 (1H, br d, *J* 11.6 Hz, H-6) and 5.09 (1H, br s, H-15).

Preferential acetylation of 6 α -hydroxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirone (15): Compound **15** (40 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) was treated with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) at about 0° and the reaction mixture was kept as such for 20 h. Dilution with ice-cold water (20 ml) was followed by acidification with dil. HCl. Extraction with chloroform (3 \times 20 ml), usual work-up and removal of chloroform gave a crude mass showing two spots in tlc. Preparative tlc of this crude mass over silica gel afforded monoacetylated compound which on crystallization gave meldonin (**4**; 22 mg), C₂₈H₃₈O₅, m.p. 240° (lit.⁴ 240-44°), [α]_D +148.8°, *R*_f 0.5; ν_{\max} 3410 (OH), 1740 (ester CO), 1685 (CO), 1385, 1360 (*gem* dimethyl), 1240 (CO-O-C), 875 (furan) cm⁻¹; δ 0.82 (3H, s, H₃-18), 0.88 (3H, s, H₃-19), 1.10 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.22 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.31 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.53 (1H, m, H_a-12), 1.56 (1H, m, H_a-11), 1.76 (3H, m, H₂-1 and H_b-11), 1.86 (1H, m, H_b-12), 2.17 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.20 (1H, m, H-9), 2.26 (1H, m, H_a-2), 2.45 (1H, m, H_a-16), 2.50 (1H, dd, *J* 14.5 and 10.3 Hz, H-16),

2.65 (1H, d, J 12.0 Hz, H-5), 2.71 (1H, m, H_b-2), 2.84 (1H, d, J 10.3 and 7.4 Hz, H-17), 4.05 (1H, br s, H-7), 5.31 (1H, br d, J 12.0 Hz, H-6), 5.58 (1H, br s, H-15), 6.29 (1H, br s, H-22), 7.27 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.39 (1H, br s, H-23); m/z 454 (M⁺, 20%), 439 (4), 410 (11), 394 (37), 379 (16), 359 (41), 214 (16), 213 (36), 146 (21), 145 (62), 136 (10), 121 (55), 81 (100). Compound 4 was also obtained by careful reduction of 6 α -acetoxydeacetylazadirone (11) following an analogous procedure.

6 α -Hydroxy-1,2-dihydrodeacetylazadirol (17) : Sodium borohydride (15 mg) was added in portions to a stirred ice-cold solution of 15 (20 mg) in methanol (2 ml) and the reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The solvent was then boiled off, the residue treated with water (20 ml) and extracted with chloroform (3 \times 20 ml). The semi-solid mass obtained was purified by column chromatography to afford 17 (16 mg), C₂₆H₃₈O₄, m.p. 191° (lit.² 188–89°), R_f 0.50 (EtOAc); ν_{\max} 3400 (OH), 1390 (*gem* dimethyl), 870 (furan) cm⁻¹; δ 0.83 (3H, s, H₃-18), 0.99 (3H, s, H₃-19), 1.03 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.18 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.35 (3H, s, H₃-28), 2.71 (1H, d, J 12.0 Hz, H-5), 2.75 (1H, m, H-17), 3.18 (1H, dd, J 10.0 and 6.0 Hz, H-3), 3.92 (1H, br s, H-7), 4.13 (H, br d, J 12.0 Hz, H-6), 5.53 (1H, m, H-15), 6.27 (1H, br s, H-22), 7.26 (1H, br s, H-21) and 7.37 (1H, br s, H-23); m/z 414 (M⁺, 24%), 396 (21), 381 (32), 363 (45), 319 (100), 213 (35).

Acetylation of triol 17 : Triol 17 (10 mg) in pyridine (0.3 ml) was treated with acetic anhydride (0.3 ml) and kept at room temperature overnight. Usual work-up afforded the triacetate 18 (9 mg), C₃₂H₄₄O₇, m.p. 163°; R_f 0.56; ν_{\max} 1725 (ester CO), 1378, 1372 (*gem* dimethyl), 1235 (C–O–CO), 865 (furan) cm⁻¹; δ 0.76 (3H, s, H₃-18), 0.90 (3H, s, H₃-19), 0.97 (3H, s, H₃-29), 1.06 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.26 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.99 (6H, s, 2 \times OCOCH₃), 2.04 (3H, s,

OCOCH₃), 2.72 (1H, d, J 12.0 Hz, H-5), 4.50 (1H, m, H-3), 5.32 (2H, m, H-7 and H-15), 5.55 (1H, dd, J 12.0 and 2.1 Hz, H-6), 6.24 (1H, m, H-22), 7.21 (1H, m, H-21) and 7.35 (1H, m, H-23).

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